

Teaching Large Classes In Historically Disadvantaged Universities: Empirical Review

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 27, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: February 28, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Higher Education; Large Class; Historically Disadvantaged Institutions</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10723482</p>	<p><i>The purpose of the study is to evaluate the impact, challenges, and possible strategies of teaching large classes in the context of historically disadvantaged institutions (HDI) of higher education in South Africa. The majority of previously disadvantaged universities are under-resourced and lack infrastructure such as adequate large lecture halls, advanced teaching and learning technologies, and a shortage of academic staff to complement the increasing number of students in the higher education sector. As a result, teaching large classes is a common practice in many South African universities, especially HDI and rural-based universities where there is high demand for higher education from rural-based students with limited spaces available. The enrolment of large classes in higher education undoubtedly adversely influences the teaching and learning process, academic performance, and subsequently the quality of graduates. This study reviews the literature on teaching large classes and expresses viable long-term solutions to the challenges of teaching large classes in HDI in South Africa. The study recommends that there ought to be greater cooperation between government, private sector, and institutions of higher learning both advanced universities and HDI to improve infrastructure and provide a conducive environment to attract many qualified academics to complement a growing demand for higher education in South Africa.</i></p>

Introduction

Teaching large classes for undergraduate studies is a common practice in many South African universities. This practice may be attributed to a lack of resources, shortage of academic staff, and lack of teaching facilities and infrastructure especially in historically disadvantaged institutions (HDI) such as the University of Zululand, University of Venda, University of Limpopo, University of Fort Hare, University of Western Cape, and Walter Sisulu University. The National Development Plan 2030 Strategy postulates that higher education in South Africa aims to attain 75% of PhD qualified academic staff, 70% student participation rates at universities, 1.62 million student enrolment, and train at least 100 PhD graduates per million people per year by 2030 (NPC, 2011). Insufficient resources and a shortage of qualified academics remain a key problematic area that derails the success of these fundamental objectives in the higher education sector.

Teaching a large class refers to a classroom environment where the number of students enrolled for a course is overcrowded. Jawitz (2013) described a large class as a classroom above a threshold of one hundred students. The total number of students enrolled in the higher education system in the world by 2030 is forecasted to rise to 414.2 million, from 99.4 million in 2000 which is an increase of 314% (Calderon and Maties, 2013). In South African universities, class sizes are increasing, not only because more students are entering tertiary institutions, but because the number of lecturers employed in higher education is not increasing commensurately. The reasons for staff stagnation are primarily related to diminishing funding support to the higher education sector (Maringe and Sing, 2014). Some universities remain under-resourced with poor infrastructure, technology, and teaching facilities, especially universities that are classified as rural-based and historically disadvantaged institutions of higher learning which adversely affect students' academic performance and the quality of graduates.

Council on Higher Education (CHE) (2015) reported that many South African universities are faced with inadequate teaching support resources in addition to poor infrastructure. As a result, large classes usually form a significant part of the first-year experience of most students at South African higher education institutions (Jawitz, 2013). Teaching a large class can be stressful for a teacher and an unpleasant learning environment for students which subsequently result to complains and unnecessary failure. Teaching large classes in HDIs remains a critical challenge for both academics and students with major concerns on shortage of academics, limited resources, and poor infrastructure.

Teaching Large Classes in Historically Disadvantaged Universities

Several HDI of higher education in South Africa are characterised by limited resources and infrastructure, and a shortage of academic staff. Hence, academics would in many instances find themselves teaching large classes, especially at the first-year level. Generally, teaching a large class can be problematic and chaotic with several challenges in the sense that it can lead to student disengagement and feelings of alienation, which can erode students' sense of responsibility and lead to behaviours that reflect a lack of commitment. Marais (2016) found that a large lecture class structure appeared to work against quality learning opportunities, commitment to active and interactive strategies, developing critical thinking skills, and high-level problem-solving capabilities. According to Hornsby et al. (2013), the growing prevalence of large class teaching and learning environments arguably adversely affects the quality of the educational experience along with poor student performance, motivation, and engagement, and impacts the ability of students to gain valuable problem-solving and higher-order critical thinking skills.

Hornsby et al. (2013) reported that large class environments are counterproductive to problem-solving and critical thinking skills which are crucial for an innovation economy and a knowledgeable society since they reinforce didactic teaching styles. Hornsby et al. (2013) further noted that a large class is not a learning environment that is conducive to establishing higher-order cognitive skills. Moreover, absenteeism and mediocre student behaviour and performance are commonly tolerated in large classes as an unfortunate reality to manage a large class. Maringe and Sing (2014) argued that students who are taught in large classes demonstrate limited thinking capacity and depend largely on a low level of learning skills, which emphasise the memory of knowledge. Students in large classes tend not only to drop out of their courses but find learning in large classes extremely challenging and usually report the highest level of dissatisfaction during the course evaluations, especially on items related to teacher-student engagement and interaction. Fortes and Tchantchane (2010) also reported that in large classes, students would experience less interaction with their teachers, leading to unnecessary failure.

Benefit of Teaching a Large Class

Several empirical studies such as Jawitz (2013), Bosser et al. (2015), and Wadesango (2021) among others, argued that teaching a large class does not only present challenges but there are also advantages that come with teaching large classes. Jawitz (2013) argued that the notion that large-class lectures in higher education are bad and should be avoided needs to be challenged. According to Jawitz (2013), large class lectures are particularly suited to providing learning experiences that motivate students by making the realistic connection between course material, personal experiences, and challenges faced by the broader society. Moreover, in large classes, there is a greater likelihood of significant clusters of students with a wide range of unique backgrounds, experiences, learning styles, or problem-solving abilities. All these clusters are valuable human resources at the disposal of the lecturer in enforcing various learning strategies to enhance the quality of teaching and learning in a large class.

An early study by Hess (2001) argued that teaching a large class is beneficial for student interaction, and there is a rich variety of human resources from different students with unique experiences, and knowledge. The emphasis is that the teacher is not the only pedagogue of the teaching and learning process because large classes are usually heterogeneous, and more proficient and excellent students can always be encouraged to assist struggling students. Furthermore, the professional development of a teacher is guaranteed as the teacher tries to discover new methods of teaching a large class.

According to Bosser et al. (2015), having many students in one classroom means more experiences, and knowledge can be shared among students. This makes the class an interesting learning environment for students to learn and a vibrant group for a teacher to teach. Bosser et al. (2015) asserted that large classes have their own synergy, where students from different backgrounds form a body of knowledge that is greater than its parts. Furthermore, large classes create an atmosphere of cooperation since students understand that the teacher cannot attend to every individual problem in the lecture, they develop a tendency to help themselves progress. Through collaboration, students feel closer to each other which helps to improve their knowledge and performance.

Challenges and Strategies of Teaching Large Classes.

- Poor student engagement and interaction

Engaging learners actively and encouraging student involvement and participation can be difficult and stressful in an overcrowded classroom. Hornsby et al. (2013) suggested that students in large classes often exhibit poor levels of engagement with the material, less commitment to the course, and a lack of confidence and motivation.

Intervention strategy: As a teacher, the best strategy would be to give assessments that promote collaboration and cooperative learning among students by giving random pair activities or group assessments to enhance participation while maintaining the quality of teaching and learning of the highest standard. Encourage students to work with those next to them to avoid time-wasting when setting up groups. Hess (2001) suggested that a

teacher can set up groups in advance and have them work together for several class activities, which avoids the time-consuming daily setups and re-organisation of groups.

- **Students at risk/inactive students**

Large classes allow reluctant and lazy students to hide behind others. These students can be classified as students at risk since teachers cannot attend to individual concerns.

Intervention strategy: The teacher can provide a variety of class activities that promote collaboration where different roles can be assigned to group members so that everyone in the group feels actively involved in the activity. For each group activity, roles must be rotated among group members, with different students acting in roles such as the group leader, facilitator, secretary, recorder, timekeeper, etc. The teacher should give clear instructions and check comprehension before the pair or group activity is assigned.

- **Giving feedback in a large class**

Large classes make it almost impossible to give effective timely feedback to students. Marking assessments for a large class is always difficult for teachers. It is always difficult to measure the effectiveness of teaching and learning in an overcrowded classroom.

Intervention strategy: A possible solution may be to diversify the structure or outline of assessments such as giving quiz tests and small group assessments to minimise the time it would take to mark assessments. The teacher can prepare handouts copies per group or pair of students. This obliges students to work together and share knowledge, and fewer copies will be needed if students work in small groups. The teacher may also need to encourage more advanced students to take the responsibility of helping others, as group leaders, mentors, monitors, or teaching assistants.

- **Classroom management of a large class**

Large classes are always difficult to manage the classroom and get students' attention during lectures. The level of noise is inevitably high during lectures which disturb other students. Zaidah (2007) found that large classes are more likely to have distracting behaviours such as coming in late, leaving early, having side conversations, texting, and students doing other activities on their gadgets. Fortes and Tchantchane (2010) also suggested that students often get distracted by the noise in large classes, and they do not get the opportunity to approach the lecturers for one-on-one consultations.

Intervention strategy: the teacher may need to work with the class representatives and all learners to establish a code of conduct that seeks to reduce the noise level in the classroom during lectures. Students are more likely to follow and respect the rules in which they were involved in establishing those rules. Some of these rules may be, for example, students should talk softly without disturbing others during group work; they should raise their hand before speaking or sharing information with the class, etc. The teacher needs to teach students rules for polite communication during class and provide clear instructions and expectations when students are working together in groups.

- **Active and interactive learning**

Large classes make it is always difficult to promote active or interactive learning when resources such as textbooks, storybooks, and reading materials are limited.

Intervention strategy: The teacher should always be available for consultations before and after class to establish personal relationships so that students can feel that they are individuals in the eyes of the teacher and motivate learners. Interactive learning can be promoted by randomly allocating students into small groups for group activities.

- **Understanding different student needs and abilities**

The planning, organization, and presentation of teaching lessons may be difficult in large classes as students' learning needs and abilities are expected to differ considerably from one student to another. Instructors ought to be cognizant of these different challenges facing students in higher education.

Intervention strategy: Prepare activities that encourage students to demonstrate their different skills and interests. Students should be aware of the goals of each learning activity and tasks must be achievable. If they understand why they are doing it, they will participate more willingly. All learning activities ought to be success-oriented to ensure that students are well aware of what is expected from them.

- **Teaching shy students in a large class**

Students tend to feel anonymous and isolated in large classes and lack confidence which makes them less likely to attend lectures regularly which may contribute to unnecessary failure. Hornsby et al. (2013) found that students are also more likely to report low level of satisfaction during course evaluations in large, lecture-based classes.

Intervention strategy: A teacher may prepare unannounced formative assessments or class activities that will be recorded to contribute a certain percentage in a year mark to discourage absenteeism among students. Sulistyowati (2012) suggested that a lecture-based large class leads to very little interaction between instructor and student, causing the student to feel anonymous, isolated, and less motivated.

Interventions at the National Level for Large Classes in HDI

The Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) and HDI ought to effectively work together to forge strategic mechanisms that seek to support low-resourced universities overcome the challenges of enrolling in large classes, such as providing financial assistance, training and development, and improving infrastructural teaching facilities.

- Provision of funding and grants

The government may provide additional funding and grants specifically targeted at low-resourced universities to improve critical infrastructure and other teaching and learning facilities to allow for large classes and technology-enhanced learning. The South African government has implemented various strategic initiatives aimed at uplifting HDIs, such as the DHET University Capacity Development Programme (UCDP) which provides funding to universities for the procurement of digital resources and devices (DHET, 2020). In addition, the National Student Financial Aid Scheme (NSFAS) has made provisions for the procurement of laptops for students who qualify for financial aid (DHET, 2020).

- Infrastructure development

Governments need to invest in improving infrastructure of low-resourced universities, including upgrading computer labs, creating a conducive space for virtual learning environments, and setting up video conferencing facilities. According to the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) report, a huge effort has been made to initiate several projects that seek to improve internet connectivity and provide necessary infrastructure such as computer labs and Wi-Fi access points in several historically disadvantaged universities (DHET, 2020). This effort is aimed at improving infrastructure of HDI to accommodate the demand for higher education in South Africa.

- Training and capacity building

Universities can organise training programmes and workshops aimed at training academic staff to develop their skills in delivering effective teaching in a blended learning environment as a solution to large classes. These initiatives should focus on building educators' capacity to design online courses, facilitate virtual lectures, and effectively utilise learning management systems and other online tools. The government through the DHET supports historically disadvantaged universities with training and development programmes through capacity-building programs and workshops to enhance teaching and learning practices in digital environments. The DHET provides funding initiatives like the University Capacity Development Programme to support the development of high-quality blended learning curricula (DHET, 2020).

Governments can also encourage low-resourced universities to establish partnerships with other well-established institutions, both domestically and internationally, to share resources, knowledge, and best practices on strategies for teaching large classes. These partnerships can provide access to expertise, resources, and shared knowledge in best practices among higher education institutions. Collaboration with private sector entities, such as technology companies, can also help universities acquire necessary equipment and software at reduced costs or through donations. Governments can offer incentives to encourage these partnerships, such as tax benefits or recognition for corporate social responsibility initiatives to promote collaboration that addresses the shortage of critical teaching and learning infrastructure in HDI.

- Research and Development Initiatives

Universities and governments can promote research and development initiatives to explore innovative approaches to teaching strategies of large classes specifically tailored to the needs of low-resourced universities. This may include solutions for low-bandwidth or low-cost technology alternatives to support online learning. Research outcomes can inform the development of targeted support programmes. Universities and governments need to create platforms for knowledge sharing and best practice exchange among universities to foster collaboration and learning from the successful experiences of other universities. The government has emphasised the importance of collaboration and knowledge sharing among universities to address blended learning challenges. These initiatives include the South African Institute for Distance Education (SAIDE) and South African Higher Education Blended Learning (SAHEBL) Communities of Practice facilitate networking and collaboration among institutions (DHET, 2020).

- Monitoring and Evaluation

Universities and governments may need to establish effective mechanisms to monitor the progress and effectiveness of teaching and learning in low-resourced universities. This allows for continuous evaluation and improvement of strategies and interventions to ensure the critical challenges of large classes with limited resources are addressed in the higher education sector. Monitoring and evaluation can involve regular evaluations of online courses, feedback collection from students and academics, benchmarking, and measuring learning outcomes. The data collected from evaluations ought to inform future policy decisions and allow for continuous improvement in the quality of teaching and learning. A comprehensive response to the challenges faced by low-resourced universities requires a multi-faceted approach, addressing financial, infrastructural, and research aspects. Providing necessary support can ensure that all HDIs have necessary and adequate teaching and learning infrastructure to provide quality higher education.

Concluding Remarks

Teaching large classes requires special training programmes which would improve necessary skills and strategies that do not only benefit the teacher's concern but also the student's ability to learn and cooperate in large classes. This can be possible through organising and planning teachers' training workshops to acquire the necessary skills and consultations with other experienced academics. Moreover, it remains imperative for higher education stakeholders such as governments, university management, and trade unions to cooperate and devise creative approaches to collaborate on issues pertaining to teaching large classes and invest much-needed resources to improve the prospects of success. The responsibility for teaching large classes should be continuously monitored by senior academics who have experience in teaching large classes. Collaboration and partnership between privileged universities and HDIs are essential to share knowledge on best practices and successful experiences in teaching large classes. Lecturers who are responsible for teaching large classes must be sufficiently resourced and well-trained, alongside other learning activities, to motivate and inspire students to pursue the discipline for students to enjoy learning experiences. Possible strategies identified must be explored to enhance the quality of teaching large classes in higher education.

References

- Bossér, U., Lundin, M., Lindahl, M., & Linder, C. (2015). Challenges Faced by Teachers Implementing Socio-Scientific Issues as Core Elements in Their Classroom Practices. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 3(2), 159-176.
- Calderon, A., & Mathies, C. (2013). Institutional research in the future: Challenges within higher education and the need for excellence in professional practice. *New Directions for Institutional Research*, 20(3), 77-90.
- Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET). (2020). University Capacity Development Programme (UCDP). Retrieved from <https://www.dhet.gov.za/SitePages/University%20Capacity%20Development%20Programme.aspx>
- Fortes, P. C., & Tchantchane, A. (2010). Dealing with large classes: A real challenge. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 8(1), 272-280.
- Hess, N. (2001). *Teaching large multilevel classes*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hornsby, DJ., & De Matos Ala, J. (2013). Promoting student engagement and deep learning approaches in large classes. In Hornsby, David., Osman, Ruksana., and De Matos Ala, Jacqueline (eds). *Large Class Pedagogy: Interdisciplinary Perspectives for Quality Higher Education*, 71-88
- Jawitz, J. (2013). *The challenge of teaching large classes in higher education in South Africa: A battle to be waged outside the classroom*. SUN MeDIA MeTRO. <http://hdl.handle.net/11427/8279>
- Marais, P. (2016). We can't believe what we see: Overcrowded classrooms through the eyes of student teachers. *South African Journal of Education*, 36(2), 1-10.
- Maringe, F., & Sing, N. (2014). Teaching large classes in an increasingly internationalising higher education environment: Pedagogical, quality and equity issues. *Higher Education*, 67(6), 761-782.
- National Planning Commission. (NPC). (2011). *National Development Plan 2030: Our future—make it work*. National Planning Commission. Retrieved from <https://www.nationalplanningcommission.org.za>.
- Sulistiyowati, T. (2012). Making large classes smaller: The challenge of teaching English to young learners in Indonesia. In *Proceeding the 2nd National Conference on Teaching English for Young Learners in Indonesia. TEYLIN: from policy to classroom*, 162-170.
- Wadesango, N. (2021). Challenges of teaching large classes. *African Perspectives of Research in Teaching and Learning*, 5(2), 127-135.
- Zaidah, Z. (2007). Case study as a research method. *Jurnal Kemanusiaan*, 5(1), 1-6.

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